

Deliverable D5.6: Report on available VMs with associated documentation/use case for each of them

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1 Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to summarize existing virtual machines (VM) and documentation about them which are available for different use cases identified during the West-life project. We report both cloud-based VMs prepared for production use and VMs appropriate for local use cases, e.g. for development, testing or private deployment purposes.

2 *Project objectives*

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Provide analysis solutions for the different Structural Biology approaches		X
2	Provide automated pipelines to handle multi-technique datasets in an integrative manner	X	
3	Provide integrated data management for single and multi-technique projects, based on existing e-infrastructure	X	
4	Foster best practices, collaboration and training of end users		X

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Structural biology research has been targeting larger and larger macromolecular machines within the cell. Their increased complexity means that researchers need to use a wide range of techniques, and expertise in order to truly exploit the various structural biology data collected. In most cases, however they are expert in only one or a few techniques and associated software. When a research project requires the use of a new experimental technique, it can be onerous to find and install software suitable for processing the data.

In task 5.4 we build custom virtual machines (VMs) for different use cases, incorporating the following software, documentation and examples:

- West-Life Virtual Folder – private instance of (WP6),
- West-Life VRE – (optional) private instance (of WP5) delivering multiuser environment, CCP4 – (optionally available after license agreement) software suite containing software tools to process data produced by X-ray crystallography methods,
- Scipion – image processing framework to process data produced mainly by electron microscopy methods.

As the software is distributed using CernVM-FS technology and accessed from within the VM, there is no need to separately update VM images in case of new software release.

An actual running Virtual Machine is referred to as an “instance”. This is created by “deploying” a VM “image”, which is a template for VM instances. By published VM images, West-Life has saved scientists the work of finding and installing suitable software.

We prepared images in two formats, suitable for OpenNebula and OpenStack, the two major virtualization environments in use in the scientific community.

Some VM images are distributed as “open virtualization appliance” (OVA) images –, packed in the open virtualization format (OVF) structure. This is compatible with e.g. VirtualBox, VMWare or OpenNebula. ([OVA images at appdb.eji.eu](http://appdb.eji.eu))

Equivalent images are also distributed as RAW image format – binary image of virtual disk and contextualization script configuring the VM after first boot. RAW image is compatible with most of other virtualization environments without direct support of OVA format, e.g. OpenStack. However, additional manual steps must to be done in order to configure the VM created from RAW image. ([RAW images in appdb.eji.eu](http://appdb.eji.eu)) OVA format seems to be supported by majority of EGI Fedcloud sites, while RAW image format may give option for the other sites. A

3.2 Cloud based VMs

One way of using these Virtual Machine images is to download one of them and run it on your own computer.

An alternative is to run it on cloud facilities. The West-Life VM Image is supported by three of the EGI FedCloud sites: IFCA-LCG(ES), CESNET-METACLOUD(CZ), INFN-PADOVA-STACK(IT).

The OCCI Client provides a way of running it on one of these sites. To do this, a scientist needs to provide these parameters:

- “site endpoint” identifying site,
- “template ID” identifying prepared instance configuration (different configurations with number of CPU and memory from small to large)
- “OCCI ID” identifying the West-life VM image.

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying the page <https://appdb.egi.eu/store/vappliance/d6.1.virtualfoldervm>. The page includes a navigation menu with 'About' and 'Contact', a search bar, and a sidebar with categories: 'Availability & Usage', 'Technical Details', 'Projects & Organizations', and 'Additional Info'. The main content area shows 'Endorsed by VO: enmr.eu' with '1 image available' and a '(view VO details)' link. Below this, there are expandable sections for 'Site: IFCA-LCG2 (ES)', 'Site: CESNET-METACLOUD (CZ)', and 'Image: ver.17.05 Scientific Linux 7.2 / x86_64 / VirtualBox'. A table lists various VM configurations with columns for Memory, Disk, Logical/Physical CPUs, Connectivity In/Out, OS Family, and a 'get IDs' button.

Memory	Disk	Logical/Physical CPUs	Connectivity In/Out	OS Family	
237568	n/a	40/40	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
65536	n/a	32/32	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
65536	n/a	16/16	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
32768	n/a	32/32	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
32768	n/a	16/16	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
32768	n/a	8/8	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
16384	n/a	4/4	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
8192	n/a	8/8	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
8192	n/a	2/2	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
4096	n/a	4/4	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
4096	n/a	1/1	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
2048	n/a	2/2	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
1024	n/a	1/1	yes/yes	linux	get IDs

CESNET-MetaCloud IDs					
Image: ver.17.05 - Scientific Linux 7.2 / x86_64 / VirtualBox					
Memory: 237568	Disk: n/a	CPU: 40/40	InOut: yes/yes	OS: linux	
Site endpoint: https://carach5.ics.muni.cz:11443					
Template ID: http://schemas.fedcloud.egi.eu/occi/infrastructure/resource_tpl#universe					
OCCL ID: http://occi.carach5.ics.muni.cz/occi/infrastructure/os_tpl#uuid_1cc39672_0f09_51da_b232_17722be1c583_warg_default_shared_198					
close					
65536	n/a	16/16	yes/yes	linux	get IDs
32768	n/a	32/32	yes/yes	linux	get IDs

Instance is contextualized by predefined cloud-init.sh script.

Both images are small (18 MB, 23 MB respectively) containing only CernVM 4 bootloader, which boots into standard Scientific Linux (currently version 7.3) and contextualizes it with West-Life specific software. Using heavy caching mechanism, (Squid is recommended by CernVM community) the most updated software binaries, including the operating system, can be delivered effectively to the end instance.

A cloudkeeper component and synchronization of the enmr.eu VM images is being tested within a private local catalog of the Resource Centre for EGI-FedCloud, in a private OpenStack environment run by partner STFC.

3.2.1 West-Life VM

This VM contains all mentioned software available at [/cvmfs/west-life.egi.eu](http://cvmfs/west-life.egi.eu) and [/cvmfs/wenmr.egi.eu](http://cvmfs/wenmr.egi.eu) (VF, Scipion, Wenmr) on CernVM 4 (which boots to Scientific Linux 7.4) with Xfce graphical desktop environment. It can be used to connect different data storages into this VM's virtual folder and process files from virtual folder using software within this VM. This VM is registered at APPDB of EGI.eu:

<https://appdb.egi.eu/store/vappliance/d6.1.virtualfoldervm>

It is distributed as OVA (open virtual appliance) image. It can be deployed into e.g. OpenNebula cloud environment.

3.2.2 West-Life VM (OpenStack)

This VM contains all mentioned software available at [/cvmfs/west-life.egi.eu](http://cvmfs/west-life.egi.eu) and [/cvmfs/wenmr.egi.eu](http://cvmfs/wenmr.egi.eu) (VF, Scipion, Wenmr) on CernVM 4 (which boots to Scientific Linux 7.4) with Xfce graphical desktop

environment. It can be used to connect different data storages into this VM's virtual folder and process files from virtual folder using software within this VM. This VM is registered at APPDB of EGI.eu:

<https://appdb.egi.eu/store/vappliance/west.life.vm>

It is distributed as RAW image. It can be deployed into e.g. OpenStack cloud environment.

3.2.3 ScipionCloud

This VM contains standalone installation of all the Scipion software tools including the GPU computing capability on Linux operating system (Ubuntu 14.04). It can be used to perform data processing on cryoEM movies and images leveraged by the option to perform selected task on GPU if available. ScipionCloud VM is registered at:

<https://appdb.egi.eu/store/vappliance/scipion.v1.0>

It is distributed as OVA image able to be deployed into e.g. OpenNebula environment.

3.3 Local based VMs for testing and development

West-Life VM can be instantiated locally from the OVA image above (<https://appdb.egi.eu/store/vappliance/d6.1.virtualfoldervm>) by importing it directly to VirtualBox.

Vagrant is a convenient tool for deploying local virtual machines. A development instance can be prepared using Vagrant tool, VirtualBox and configuration scripts at <https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-vm>. Full instructions are at <https://h2020-westlife-eu.gitbooks.io/virtual-folder-docs/content/doc/installation-guide/development-installation.html>

3.3.1 Standalone Virtual Folder VM from source codes

This VM contains all mentioned software available at /cvmfs/west-life.egi.eu and /cvmfs/wenmr.egi.eu (VF, Scipion, Wenmr) on CernVM 4 (which boots to Scientific Linux 7.4) with Xfce graphical desktop environment. This VM is based on CernVM 4.0 micro image size = 18MB, during boot and bootstrap downloads 658 MB. This is preferred option as CernVM distributes most updated SL7 with recent security updates, so either restart or ``cernvm-update -a`` is required occasionally.

```
git clone https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-vm.git
cd wp6-vm/vf-standalone-src/
vagrant up
```

3.3.2 Standalone Virtual Folder VM from binaries (distributed via cvmfs)

The same as above - but Virtual Folder is not compiled from sources. Binaries are used at from /cvmfs/west-life.egi.eu. This option is faster, the last stable release is distributed.

```
git clone https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-vm.git
cd wp6-vm/vf-standalone-bin/
vagrant up
```

3.3.3 Standalone Virtual Folder from source codes at SL7

The same as in section 3.3.1 but based directly on Scientific Linux 7 (instead of CernVM 4 micro image) and without access to software at /cvmfs. No dependency on online repositories at all. Initial VM image size = 665 MB, boot and bootstrap download 320 MB. This configuration is recommended for preparing off-line deployment.

```
git clone https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-vm.git
cd wp6-vm/vf-standalone-src-sl7/
vagrant up
```

3.3.4 Repository Instance from source codes

This VM contains development version of West-Life D6.2 Repository on Scientific Linux 7.4 with graphical desktop environment. It can be used to test compatibility with particular software available at institution who would like to have installation of the D6.2 Repository.

```
git clone https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-vm.git
cd wp6-vm/rep-standalone-src-sl7/
vagrant up
```

3.3.5 Test configurations

These VMs contain deployment of third party product on supported CernVM or Scientific Linux 7.4 with graphical desktop environment. They can be used to test compatibility with particular software on the operating system used by West-Life VM.

```
git clone https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-vm.git
cd wp6-vm/test-...
vagrant up
```


3.4 Generic VMs

As there was no vagrant box for CernVM 4 or Scientific Linux 7.4, vagrant boxes were published with generic virtual machine templates, which can be used to further prepare development environments as described in section 3.3 or updated production VM templates described in section 3.2. Images were created and can be downloaded from <https://app.vagrantup.com/westlife-eu>

3.4.1 CernVM 4

The CernVM 4 box allows creating VM based on CernVM which boots to Scientific Linux 7 delivered by distributed web technology cernvm.cern.ch. Box is available at <https://app.vagrantup.com/westlife-eu/boxes/cernvm4> and can be referred as `westlife-eu/cernvm4` in Vagrantfile:

```
config.vm.box = "westlife-eu/cernvm4"
```

In contrast to official <https://app.vagrantup.com/cernvm/boxes/4-preview> it boots into graphical user interface, which is required by some West-Life related legacy software.

3.4.2 Scientific Linux 7.x

The Scientific Linux 7 box contains currently scientific Linux 7.4). Box is available at https://app.vagrantup.com/westlife-eu/boxes/scientific_7_x86_64_minimal_gui and can be referred as `westlife-eu/scientific_7_x86_64_minimal_gui` in Vagrantfile:

```
config.vm.box = "westlife-eu/scientific_7_x86_64_minimal_gui"
```

Appendix

Log of the VM deployment from source codes (see section 3.3.1).

```
CLRC+ras23654@ras23654del1 MI NGW64 ~/Projects-local/test
$ git clone https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-vm.git
Cloning into 'wp6-vm'...
remote: Counting objects: 235, done.
remote: Compressing objects: 100% (16/16), done.
sed 14 (delta 3), pack-reused 215
Receiving objects: 100% (235/235), 44.01 KiB | 0 bytes/s, done.
Resolving deltas: 100% (126/126), done.
Checking connectivity... done.

CLRC+ras23654@ras23654del1 MI NGW64 ~/Projects-local/test
$ cd wp6-vm

CLRC+ras23654@ras23654del1 MI NGW64 ~/Projects-local/test/wp6-vm (master)
$ cd vf-standalone-src

CLRC+ras23654@ras23654del1 MI NGW64 ~/Projects-local/test/wp6-vm/vf-standalone-src
(master)
$ vagrant up
vagrant version:
1.9.6
vagrant forward ports set
Bringing machine 'default' up with 'virtualbox' provider...
==> default: Importing base box 'westlife-eu/cernvm4'...
==> default: Matching MAC address for NAT networking...
==> default: Checking if box 'westlife-eu/cernvm4' is up to date...
==> default: Setting the name of the VM: vf-standalone-src_default_1508325785181_59651
==> default: Fixed port collision for 22 => 2222. Now on port 2202.
==> default: Clearing any previously set network interfaces...
==> default: Preparing network interfaces based on configuration...
    default: Adapter 1: nat
==> default: Forwarding ports...
    default: 80 (guest) => 8083 (host) (adapter 1)
    default: 8000 (guest) => 8003 (host) (adapter 1)
    default: 22 (guest) => 2202 (host) (adapter 1)
==> default: Running 'pre-boot' VM customizations...
==> default: Booting VM..
==> default: Waiting for machine to boot. This may take a few minutes...
    default: SSH address: 127.0.0.1:2202
    default: SSH username: vagrant
    default: SSH auth method: private key
```

References cited

<https://cernvm.cern.ch/> CernVM – is a Virtual Machine distributed as a micro bootloader (typically under 20 MB). The rest of an operating system and other tools are loaded using CernVM-FS technology on request.

<https://cernvm.cern.ch/portal/filesystem> CernVM-FS – read only filesystem technology to distribute software.

<https://appdb.egi.eu/> AppDB - The EGI Applications Database (AppDB) is a central service that stores and provides to the public information about software solutions

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_Virtualization_Format - OVF, OVA – Open Virtual Appliance

<https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/west-life-wp6> - source codes of West-Life Virtual Folder

<https://github.com/h2020-westlife-eu/wp6-repository> - source codes of West-Life Repository

<https://h2020-westlife-eu.gitbooks.io/virtual-folder-docs/content/> - installation guide containing instruction how to use virtual folder and related VM

<https://www.vagrantup.com/> - Vagrant is a tool for building and managing virtual machine environments in a single workflow.

<https://www.virtualbox.org/> - VirtualBox is open source hypervisor – creates and runs virtual machines.

<https://openebula.org/> - is cloud computing environment

<https://www.openstack.org/> - is cloud computing environment

<https://h2020-westlife-eu.gitbooks.io/virtual-folder-docs/content/doc/installation-guide/cloud-installation.html> - Installation guide for deployment in a cloud computing environment